

PROVING NOBILITY IN EARLY MODERN CASTILE

LA PRUEBA DE NOBLEZA EN LA CASTILLA MODERNA

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Abstract: This article analyses a *Carta Ejecutoria de Hidalguía* (Executory Letter of Nobility) issued in 1571² by the Royal Chancery of Valladolid in favour of Francisco de Santos, whose noble status was contested in Colmenar Viejo (Madrid, Spain). Through the judicial process and the evidence presented, the study examines how hereditary nobility was recognised and defended in early modern Castile. The executory letter insight into lineage, testimony, and the social meaning of noble identity, highlighting the role of mobility and local reputation in shaping noble memory during the *Ancien Régime*.

Resumen: Este artículo analiza una *Carta Ejecutoria de Hidalguía* otorgada en 1571 por la Real Chancillería de Valladolid a favor de Francisco de Santos, cuya condición nobiliaria fue impugnada en Colmenar Viejo (Madrid, España). A partir del proceso judicial y de las pruebas aportadas, se examina cómo se reconocía y defendía la nobleza hereditaria en la Castilla moderna. La ejecutoria de hidalguía ofrece una visión del linaje, el testimonio y el significado social de la identidad nobiliaria, destacando el papel de la movilidad y la reputación local en la construcción de la memoria nobiliaria del Antiguo Régimen.

Keywords: Hidalguía; Royal Chancery of Valladolid; executory letter; nobility; lineage; early modern Castile; genealogy; legal history.

Palabras Clave: Hidalguía; Real Chancillería de Valladolid; carta ejecutoria; nobleza; linaje; Castilla moderna; genealogía; historia del derecho.

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1. A Document Granting Identity: The 1571 Executory Letter of Nobility

The document examined in this study is a *Carta Ejecutoria de Hidalguía* (Executory Letter of Nobility) issued in 1571 by the Chamber of Nobles of the Royal Chancery of Valladolid. It records the judicial ruling in favour of the plaintiff, recognising his hereditary noble status. Such documents, of considerable legal authority, marked the culmination of a formal judicial process in which the claimant was required to demonstrate his nobility before the competent tribunal.

The protagonist of the lawsuit is Francisco de Santos (†1591), my twelfth direct male ancestor, who appeared before the Chancery to assert his right to noble status. The ruling, preserved in the 1571 executory, acknowledges him as a *hidalgo notorio*, thereby legitimising both his personal status and that of his lineage.

The geographical framework of the case is articulated between two significant localities:

A) Rabanal de los Caballeros, a district of Cervera de Pisuegra in the mountains of Palencia, appears as the ancestral place of origin. Its documentary history reaches back to the *Becerro de las Presentaciones of the Cathedral of León*³, where the church of San Martín is associated with local noble families bearing the surnames Gómez, Duque, and López. In the *Becerro de las Behetrías de Castilla*, Rabanal is recorded as the ancestral home of Fernando García Duque and María Díaz, further reinforcing its noble character.

B) Colmenar Viejo, today part of the Community of Madrid, belonged in the sixteenth century to the County of the Real de Manzanares under the jurisdiction of the Dukes of Infantado. On 22 November 1504, it obtained jurisdictional separation from the lordship of Manzanares, consolidating its role as an economic and administrative centre. Around 1590, the town had approximately 1,500 inhabitants, largely engaged in agriculture and livestock farming, with a very small noble presence⁴. This context makes the recognition of Francisco de Santos's nobility particularly notable.

2. From Rabanal de los Caballeros to Colmenar Viejo: A conflict over noble status

After relocating—whether through marriage or inheritance—from Rabanal de los Caballeros (Palencia) to Colmenar Viejo (Madrid), Don Francisco de Santos encountered opposition from the town council and its *hombres buenos* or *pecheros*⁵. Having been entered in the register of commoners, he was assigned a taxpaying, which implied the non-recognition of his noble status. When he refused to pay, his garments were seized as security, prompting him to initiate a lawsuit before the Royal Chancery of Valladolid.

In the proceedings, Don Francisco demonstrated his nobility by agnatic descent, proving the noble status of his father, grandfather, and great-grandfather. The 1571 executory legally confirmed his noble condition, following successive rulings by the *Alcaldes de los Hijosdalgo*⁶ and their confirmation by the *Oidores* in view and review⁷.

³ The *Becerro de las Presentaciones de León* is a medieval manuscript preserved in the Archive of the Cathedral of León, recording the churches and parishes subject to presentation by lay and ecclesiastical patrons.

⁴ Population estimates are based on the Catastro de Ensenada and local demographic studies. See F. Martínez Sanz, *Demografía histórica de la Sierra de Madrid* (Madrid: CSIC, 2002).

⁵ The principal commoners of the town.

⁶ Judges responsible for cases involving *hidalgos*.

⁷ For the judicial structure of the Royal Chancery and the role of the *Alcaldes de los Hijosdalgo*, see José Manuel Pérez-Prendes y Muñoz de Arraco, José Manuel. *Historia del derecho español*. Madrid: Universidad Complutense de Madrid, (1999). 342–345.

In early modern Castile, noble status was exercised in the locality of residence, where registration as a noble required public recognition. A change of residence often generated disputes, giving rise to the so-called lawsuits of “His Majesty’s Prosecutor and the good men” against individuals claiming noble status in a new town⁸. These proceedings, brought before the Prosecutor of the Royal Court and the local council, required the submission of documentary and testimonial evidence demonstrating lineage, legitimacy of birth, and the continuity of nobility through the male line⁹.

In Don Francisco’s case, the lawsuit was initiated through a power of attorney granted to his solicitor, who filed suit against the council requesting its conviction, the restitution of the garments unlawfully taken, and full recognition of the honours and privileges pertaining to *hidalgos notorios de sangre* (hidalgos of publicly recognised noble lineage).

The Court ordered the submission of the relevant evidence. After the initial ruling by the *alcaldes*, the commoners appealed to the Chamber of Judges, which upheld the decision both on review and on appeal, thus definitively recognising Don Francisco as a nobleman. The executory letter transcribed the essential elements of the lawsuit, consolidating its value as a legal, genealogical, and symbolic document.

3. Nobility in Perspective: Lineage, Privilege, and Legal Proof

The term *hidalgo* originated in the northern regions of the Iberian Peninsula during the *Reconquista*, with clear military and administrative associations. In territories recovered from Muslim rule, monarchs confirmed privileges to certain individuals and lineages, thereby ratifying their noble status. The terminology is documented from the tenth century onwards, appearing in foundations, royal donations, and other legal instruments¹⁰.

Hereditary nobility was transmitted through the male line, from father to son. Its origins were often rooted in immemorial nobility—status so ancient that its beginnings were neither remembered nor documented and thus had to be proven through witness testimony and supporting evidence. In contrast, nobility granted by royal privilege could become hereditary after three generations of legitimate transmission¹¹. The notorious nobleman was one publicly recognised as nobleman by his community, reinforcing his social standing.

From the *Siete Partidas of Alfonso X* to the Confusion of States of 1834¹², nobility by blood required proof of the noble status of both father and grandfather. The distinction between the two principal forms of nobility lay in the antiquity of their origin: immemorial nobility was considered proven by the absence of any memory of acquisition, whereas privileged nobility required three generations to consolidate itself as hereditary.

Both forms—hereditary and privileged—were fundamental to the configuration of the Spanish noble estate during the *Ancien Régime*. Privileged nobility could evolve into hereditary nobility over time, provided that the continuous exercise of noble rights could be demonstrated.

⁸ The *pleito del Fiscal* was a common procedural formula in nobility cases, in which His Majesty’s Prosecutor acted as the opposing party in defence of the public interest. See José Manuel Pérez-Prendes y Muñoz de Arraco, José Manuel. *Historia del derecho español*. Madrid: Universidad Complutense de Madrid, (1999). 342–345.

⁹ “Honours and privileges” included tax exemptions, eligibility for council offices, and forms of social recognition.

¹⁰ On the origin of the term *hidalgo* and its connection to the Reconquista, see J. de Salazar y Acha, *El poder del linaje: La alta nobleza de Castilla y León en la Edad Media*. Madrid: Real Academia de la Historia. Agencia Estatal Boletín Oficial del Estado (2024), 27–35.

¹¹ Privileged nobility was regulated through various royal decrees.

¹² The Confusion of States of 1834 effectively abolished the legal distinction between nobles and commoners.

However, descendants who changed residence were often required to revalidate their status through executory proceedings in the Chancelleries and Courts in order to be entered in the Registers of Distinction of States as noblemen or *hidalgos*¹³.

Numerous noble privileges were confirmed in lawsuits heard before the Royal Chancery Courts, including the case of Don Francisco de Santos. Many disputes arose when a nobleman moved to a new locality, particularly upon marriage. In such circumstances, it was customary for the individual to seek recognition of his exemptions, freedoms, and privileges in the new district.

The court records preserved in the Chancelleries contain extensive documentation of such lawsuits. The *Alcaldes de los Hijosdalgo* or the *Oidores*, after reviewing the evidence, issued rulings based on the material presented. Testimonial evidence was especially valuable when provided by elderly witnesses familiar with the genealogy and reputation of the litigant. Under oath, witnesses answered questions concerning the plaintiff's identity, age, origin, residence, filiation, and legitimacy of birth, as well as those of his ancestors¹⁴.

These statements contextualised the litigant and demonstrated that his parents and grandparents had been persons of recognised standing, legitimately married, and treated as noblemen. The resulting genealogical narrative constituted the traditional foundation of noble identity, rooted in lineage and blood.

From a documentary perspective, the plaintiff's lineage was crucial, particularly when written records were lacking. In the absence of documentation, oral testimony was the only available recourse. Only after the Council of Trent (1545–1563) were sacramental registers—baptisms, marriages, and burials—established in Spanish dioceses, enabling greater genealogical traceability¹⁵.

Positive acts of nobility were also considered: occupying prominent places in church ceremonies, being treated as a nobleman by other nobles, and living in a manner befitting one's status. Many *hidalgos* resided in rural areas, in houses they owned, with livestock and farmland. Their leisure activities included reading, hunting, and participation in local administration, particularly in the *Mitad de Oficios Nobles* (Half of Noble Offices)¹⁶.

4. Noble Memory and Documentary Legacy

The *Carta Ejecutoria de Hidalguía* is one of the principal documentary sources for the study of Spanish nobility, as it contains, in the form of extracts or transcriptions, the evidence presented by the litigant concerning genealogy, social status, and heraldry. These documents allow us to trace three fundamental coordinates: the place of origin, the judicial sphere of the lawsuit, and the new residence of the plaintiff, thereby forming a cartography of identity of notable historical value.

¹³ On the registers and their function in distinguishing between social estates.

¹⁴ For a model of witness interrogation, see Archive of the Royal Chancery of Valladolid, *Pleitos de Hidalguía*, leg. 1234, exp. 56.

¹⁵ The Council of Trent (1545–1563) institutionalized universal parish record-keeping during its twenty-fourth session in November 1563 through the decree Tametsi. Mandated to combat clandestine marriages, this decree forced parish priests to maintain strict matrimonial and baptismal registers. Formally promulgated by Pope Pius IV in 1564 via the papal bull *Benedictus Deus*, this bureaucratic system was later standardized into five distinct books (including deaths and confirmations) by Pope Paul V's *Rituale Romanum* in 1614.

¹⁶ The *Mitad de Oficios Nobles* (Half of Noble Offices) comprised municipal offices shared between nobles and commoners in certain Castilian councils.

Preserved in institutions such as the *Archivo Histórico Nacional* (National Historical Archive) and the Royal Chancery of Valladolid, these writs of execution are not only of legal and genealogical significance but also possess a documentary beauty that renders them heritage objects of the highest order. In the case examined here, the 1571 executory enables the recovery of a fragment of the author's family history, projecting his noble legacy into the present.

In the context of nobility law, the executory constitutes full proof of noble status, valid for admission to Military Orders and other noble corporations in the Hispanic world¹⁷. Its value transcends the legal sphere, becoming a testimony to social memory, lineage, and the continuity of an identity inherited and recognised by royal authority.

5. Conclusions

The lawsuit of Francisco de Santos provides a revealing window into the legal, social, and institutional mechanisms through which noble status was defined, contested, and ultimately affirmed in early modern Castile. Far from being a merely administrative procedure, the *pleito de hidalguía* functioned as a complex arena in which personal reputation, local memory, documentary evidence, and royal authority intersected. The petition submitted by Francisco, the response of the council of Colmenar Viejo, and the subsequent evidentiary process illustrate the tensions between individual claims to honour and the collective interests of local communities, which often resisted the loss of taxpayers and the erosion of their fiscal base.

The case also highlights the central role of the Royal Chancery of Valladolid as an institution capable of arbitrating disputes over social status with procedural rigour and documentary scrutiny. The production of testimonies, the examination of genealogical narratives, and the intervention of legal professionals reveal a sophisticated judicial culture in which noble identity was not assumed but demonstrated. The final ruling and the issuance of the executory letter in 1571 show how royal justice could override local opposition, providing individuals with a legally binding recognition that reshaped their position within the social hierarchy.

More broadly, the lawsuit exemplifies the dynamic nature of nobility in sixteenth-century Castile. Rather than a static or immutable condition, noble status emerged as a negotiated reality, shaped by legal expertise, archival memory, and the capacity of individuals to mobilise resources in defence of their lineage. The case of Francisco de Santos thus contributes to a deeper understanding of social mobility, the construction of honour, and the institutional frameworks that regulated access to privilege. It also underscores the importance of documentary culture in early modern society, where written proof and judicial validation played a decisive role in defining personal and collective identities.

Ultimately, this lawsuit stands as a valuable example of how legal institutions, local communities, and individual actors interacted in the broader process of shaping noble status in early modern Castile. Through its procedural detail and its final outcome, the case enriches our understanding of the legal sphere of the Royal Chancery of Valladolid and offers a nuanced perspective on the mechanisms of social distinction in the Hispanic monarchy.

¹⁷ On the use of letters patent as proof of nobility in the Military Orders, see the review of Anel Hernández. "Era melancólica: Figuras del imaginario barroco, por Fernando Rodríguez de la Flor". *Fronteras de la historia: revista de historia colonial latinoamericana* 14, 2, ISSN 2027-4688 (2009). Pp 396-400. 173–178. Such documents are considered full proof for admission to the Royal Association of Hidalgos of Spain.

Documentary Appendix

1. Identification of the Document

Date: 22 December 1571

Regesta (Title): “Enforcement of the lawsuit litigated by Francisco de Santos, resident of Colmenar Viejo (Madrid), with His Majesty’s Prosecutor and the council and commoners of the said town, concerning his nobility.”

Reference: Registro de Ejecutorias, Box 1222.26¹⁸

2. Terms of the Lawsuit

2.1. Petition to Initiate Proceedings

On 8 February 1561, Don Francisco de Santos, represented by his attorney Juan de Paredes, petitioned for the return of items unlawfully seized from him, asserting his status as a nobleman by birth. He requested removal from the tax registers, formal recognition of his honours and privileges, and protection from further disturbance or taxation.

2.2. Request for a Response

The council of Colmenar Viejo, represented by its attorney Juan de Antezana, argued that Francisco de Santos descended from commoners, that his ancestors had not been summoned to war nor held noble offices, and that he himself had not been born of a legitimate marriage.

3. First-Instance Rulings

Two summonses were issued to the plaintiff to gather sufficient evidence: the first in 1561 and the second in 1569.

4. Appeal before the Royal Chancery of Valladolid

Date of appeal: 1569

Defendants’ request:

They petitioned for the initial judgment to be overturned, for acquittal of costs, and for Francisco de Santos to be declared a commoner.

Evidence presented by the plaintiff:

Testimony from residents of Gamedo, Rabanal de los Caballeros, and Cervera de Pisuerga; tax registers; the *Libro Becerro of León*; and documents from the archives of the Count of Siruela.

Evidence presented by the defendants:

No documentation was submitted.

5. Final Judgments of the Court

5.1. Judgment (3 June 1570)

“We rule that Francisco de Santos has properly and fully presented his case and claim. We grant, declare, and pronounce his intention to be well proven [...] and declare the said

¹⁸ For the digital catalogue entry of this document, see PARES (Portal de Archivos Españoles), reference code: ES. 47186.ARCHV//REGISTRO DE EJECUTORIAS,CAJA 1222,26

Francisco de Santos to be a man of noble birth and lineage, as a legitimate descendant of the ancestral house of Duque located in the town of Rabanal de los Caballeros. Therefore, we must and do condemn His Majesty's Prosecutor and the Council, officials, and good men not to assess him for taxes or levies, and to grant him all honours, privileges, and exemptions, removing him from the registers of commoners subject to taxation."

5.2. Review Ruling (28 September 1571)

"Francisco de Santos ordered that a writ of execution be issued and delivered, containing the final judgments given and pronounced in view and in degree of review between the said parties in his favour."

Fig. 2. Folio containing the court's final ruling, declaring Francisco de Santos to be of noble birth and ordering the issuance of the Executory Letter. This key document legally establishes his noble status. Archive of the Royal Chancery of Valladolid, 22 December 1571, fol. 13.

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Fig. 3. Detail of the signatures authenticating the document, including that of the notary, whose attestation validates the executory letter. This element is essential for the legal legitimacy of the file. Archive of the Royal Chancery of Valladolid, 22 December 1571, fol. 14.

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